

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IBEJI****FIRST NAME: MAOBUGHICHI****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA – 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: RP 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used the following software: (MSWord on Windows 10)

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have been fascinated by the teaching and knowledge building model adopted by EUCLID in taking graduate students through the rudiments of academic writing, which I have dubbed; *Writing 101* because, it covers the basic and rudimentary aspects of academic writing, especially for me who had become a bit rusty, and not written an academic paper in very recent times. As rudimentary as this phase of study may seem, it has given me great insight about how important basic understanding of writing skills could be in helping to achieve high quality and presentable academic papers. It buttresses the point that; An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2015, 2).

The contents and presentation of reading materials by EUCLID have equally made it easy to understand. It equally captures the essence of writing essays and goes ahead to offer direct interactive approaches to achieving high level skills in writing essays or research papers at various stages. I consider these approaches very salient in creating good writing culture and the required discipline to keep to rules that govern the art of writing. These are in line with the fact that; An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources (EUCLID 2015, 2).

I have no doubt it will be of great help to me in providing the required and necessary guidance to achieving great writing skills, which will be beneficial to me in the course of writing my thesis and future academic papers as a professional.

2) PERIOD ONE (1) COURSEPACK

The coursepack is an eighty-three-page document which buttresses the basics of essay writing. It encapsulates the rudiments of essay writing and lays out simplified sequence of application and comprehension on how to initiate, proceed and conclude an essay. It teaches what a good essay requires and the basic steps to follow to accomplish such, starting from the initial planning phase, where a clear definition of what is to be accomplished by the essay is highlighted.

EUCLID *Coursepack, ACA-401D*, points out that some basic steps need to be followed in writing a good essay (2).

The basic steps are as follows:

- Analyse the question and define key terms
- Establish a possible thesis/ point of view
- Research the topic. Use credible academic sources for support and evidence
- Take notes from your readings
- Write an essay plan and organise your ideas
- Write your first draft to include your introduction, body and conclusion
- Set the draft aside for a day or two, then read it through and make changes
- Edit and redraft your essay
- Have a friend/parent/colleague read it
- Complete or check your references and bibliography
- Final draft completed - hand it in

As a guide, emphasis is made on the need and importance of researching a topic, as well as undertaking extensive reading of the researched topic to gain full clarity and understanding of same, while taking comprehensive notes to help achieve a more organised and well thought approach to writing the essay in the most acceptable manner. On the other hand, it highlighted that essay writing requires creative and critical thinking, which encourages the writer to adopt broad techniques like; brainstorming and mind mapping, as well as narrowing the focus or scope of ideas to streamline the argument (EUCLID 2015, 3).

In all, it teaches me that essay writing should encompass both creative and critical thinking where creative thinking encourages me to broaden my ideas and try techniques like brainstorming or mind mapping. Critical thinking encourages me to narrow the focus or scope of my ideas (EUCLID 2015, 3).

I have learned that an essay is best structured through the initial stage of introduction, before writing the body, which offers exposition to buttress the purpose of writing, before the conclusion is made based on buttressed facts, which generally restates the answer to the initial question asked at the introductory stage. Subsequently, referencing is carried out, in order to highlight the sources of information and data used in writing the essay because, no academic essay or paper should be writing without

referencing through the recommended or acceptable style. All academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence (EUCLID 2015, 5).

3) STYLE OF WRITING

Part of the highlighted learning is the importance of style in writing and how it is achieved by stipulating the guidelines to follow, depending on whether the writer is using the US or UK spelling and punctuation in a consistent manner. My ability to understand the need to be consistent in style of writing is important because, it gives room for uniformity in spelling, especially in the process of running spell checks through the system. The essay should include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant aspects of a particular topic (EUCLID 2015, 3).

On the other hand, I have learned about the importance of acknowledging sources of information and data in order to avoid plagiarism; which is considered a major offence in academic writing because, it is a situation where I use the intellectual property of another writer, without acknowledging or citing the used information or data. In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using (EUCLID 2015, 3).

Citing of sources of information or data may be in the form of in-text; which refers to citing the piece of work that is being used within the actual text. In-text methods can be cited using methods like; quotations and paraphrases, where quotations mean using the exact words of the author. In the case of quotation, EUCLID developed a peculiar template which depicts the quoted portion in the form of indented paragraph. In academic writing, it is advised to minimise the use of quotations because, written papers are expected to maintain their originality. When you use a quotation you must use quotation marks “ ” to capture what the author has said (EUCLID 2015, 19).

On the other hand, paraphrases are words or information that I may produce in my own words, bearing in mind that academic writing should have semblance of originality in content. Despite highlighting the importance of citing in academic papers, it should be noted that, it is not everything that should be cited. Some facts are common knowledge and will be superfluous if cited. It is therefore imperative for me to understand the format to follow in organising my work to ensure uniformity. Paraphrases are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in **your** own words (EUCLID 2015, 23).

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism and web copywriting (EUCLID 2015, 52).

3) LITERATURE REVIEW

I understand the importance of literature review in writing essay or academic papers because, it could rightly be considered as the main body of the essay, which shows my ability to read extensively on the subject or topic. It teaches and encourages me to read extensively, in order to build a very robust knowledge base considering that there is no single style to carry out research because; The lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means that there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on elements of style (EUCLID 2015, 52).

However, EUCLID has provided guidance in a very articulate manner, thereby reinforcing the importance of understanding the rudiments of writing which may look simple, but very important and pertinent to being able to write a world class academic paper or essay. The guidance to choose whether to use America or United Kingdom mode of English is worth noting, in order to achieve consistency in the writing process. Other important aspects like understanding when and where to use punctuations and dates, and also being able to design analytical framework within the context of the thesis, makes the academic work very robust and research compliant. There is no doubt that such ability will impact on my ability to design a career path with well-articulated Curriculum Vitae, having understood and analysed humongous amount of literature in the course of presenting my academic writing or essay. This is most imperative because; knowledge empowers any individual who seeks to know.

4) CONCLUSION

Having studied the coursepack, there is no doubt on my mind that it contains simple, but very important aspects of writing essays, and most importantly, writing academic papers because, it spells out and provides guidance on what to do in all aspects of writing a meaningful paper. I understand the structure and sequence an academic essay should take and how important it is to stay focused on the points on which the academic paper is being written on.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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